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MUSES Project

Title:

Final Conference Report

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List of Acronyms

DABI – Drivers, Added Value, Barriers, negative Impacts
EU – European Union
IC(Z)M – Integrated Coastal (Zone) Management
MPA – Marine Protected Area
MSEG – Member States Expert Group
MSP – Marine Spatial Planning
MU – Multi-Use
MUSES – Multi-Use in European Seas
NGO – Non-Governmental Organisation
UCH – Underwater Cultural Heritage

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1. Introduction

In October 2018, the MUSES Project held its final conference in Brussels in order to disseminate project results and discuss the way forward for multi-use in European Seas. Engaging a wide range of interested stakeholders from the business community, public administrations and academia, the conference provided a platform for discussion of our EU-wide Multi-Use Action Plan, setting out the various actions that can be taken at different levels (including policy, administration, legislation etc.) to promote multi-use in European Seas. Presentations and discussions also covered findings from multi-use case studies and sea basin analysis from the project partners. Stakeholders and actors with certain roles in the development of multi-use concepts and its implementation also presented their experiences and perspectives on multi-use. The conference was designed to encourage discussions and potential partnerships that would support the implementation of the action plan and advance the development of the multi-use concept across the EU. This report outlines the conference invitation and dissemination procedures, conference sessions and associated discussions, and concludes with the key conference outcomes and follow-up.

The conference took place on 10th October 2018 at Crowne Plaza Le Palace in Brussels (Belgium). This date was chosen to coincide with the 15th meeting of the Member States expert group (MSEG) on Maritime Spatial Planning on 8th and 9th October in order to increase participation of various actors relevant for promoting multi-use who would already be in Brussels. Attendees of this meeting were invited to the MUSES Final Conference via a representative at Directorate General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries.

Invitation letters were sent to our project database of approximately 450 multi-use stakeholders, including all those invited to previous MUSES Project workshops in Poole (May 2017), Dundee (April 2018) and Venice (June 2018), as well as recommendations from stakeholders, project partners and Project Officer at the European Commission. Specific multi-use actors, recommended by project partners to play an active part in the Final Conference, were sent personalised invitations, asking them to consider a speaker/ panellist/ discussion lead role.

Invited stakeholders comprised of representatives from a diverse range of areas, including: international organisations, national bodies, scientific institutions, NGO's, environmental associations, management bodies, MSP, IC(Z)M authorities, industry and regional bodies, Maritime sectors (i.e. wind and wave energy, aquaculture, tourism transportation, etc.), with different institutional roles (policy-making, environmental protection, industry, research/scientific, safety and/or control, planning) and covering all European Sea basins (Eastern Atlantic Ocean, North Sea, Baltic Sea, Mediterranean and Black Sea).

The conference was also publicised widely on the official MUSES website and social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn) and through the websites, blogs and social media

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platforms of partner organisations, both before registration opened and after registration went live. An external blog piece was also published about the MUSES Project by Scottish Renewables which highlighted the Final Conference.

2. Final Conference: Presentations, Panels and Round Table Discussions

2.1 Welcome Address

The Welcome Address was given by **Matthijs Soede** of Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG Research) who spoke about the pertinence of a multi-use approach in contemporary Europe, especially given the publication of the most recent IPCC report on Climate Change. In terms of supporting the development of multi-use, it is important to focus not only on the technological aspects, but also on those related to regulation, legal issues, permits and finance. Dr Soede emphasised the importance of a vision for the long term, with support from multiple levels (EU, national, local) in order to develop the sea in an efficient and coordinated manner. The address concluded with an invitation to participants to engage with the day's presentations and to consider disseminating the information gained with those from outside the conference community in order to facilitate the actions required to promote future multi-use.

Figure 1: Welcome Address given by Dr Matthijs Soede

2.2 Introduction to the MUSES Project and methodological framework

Bruce Buchanan (MUSES Project Coordinator) started by briefly introducing the MUSES Project, the consortium partners and the project aims and objectives (Figure 2). This was followed by a brief overview of the MUSES methodology, the overall structure of the project and concluded with a few words on what to expect from the Final Conference. **Maximilian Felix Schupp** (Alfred Wegener Institute) then gave a short explanation of the MUSES Project's key definitions of "marine multi-use", "use", "user" and "resource".

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Figure 2: Introduction given by MUSES Project Coordinator, Bruce Buchanan

2.3 Session 1: MUSES Evidence Base – Sea Basin Analysis & Case Studies

2.3.1 Presentations from MUSES Partners

Overview of Multi-Use combinations: Rich Picture of concepts and approaches to development

Angela Schultz-Zehden, Ivana Lukic & Joseph (Kofi) Ansong (SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth) guided participants through the “rich picture” of multi-uses in European seas (Figure 3), summarising the main forms, opportunities and limitations for the following nine multi-use combinations explored in the Action Plan:

- Tourism, fisheries and environmental protection
- Tourism, underwater cultural heritage and environmental protection
- Tourism and aquaculture
- Offshore wind farm and tourism
- Offshore wind farm and fisheries
- Offshore wind farm and aquaculture
- Oil and Gas and other uses
- Offshore wave energy and aquaculture
- Offshore wind and marine renewable energy

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Figure 3: Rich Picture of Multi-Uses

Main opportunities and challenges of Multi-Use: Sea basins & case study areas

Joanna Przedzmirska (Maritime Institute in Gdansk) and **Emiliano Ramieri**, (THETIS Spa) presented on the MUSES research into multi-use in the five European sea basins (North Sea, Black sea, Baltic sea, Mediterranean Sea and Eastern Atlantic Ocean) and 10 in-depth case studies. These two streams of research had the common aim to (i) explore the variety of MU experiences and possibilities across different European Seas and in site-specific locations and identify most promising MU combinations; (ii) provide knowledge on what are the maritime sectors that could drive MU development; (iii) identify MU potential (Drivers and Barriers), as well as effects (Added Values and Impacts) on the environmental-socio-economic system (DABI); and (iv) inform the Action Plan with relevant issues for MU promotion. This was achieved through extensive desk analysis and stakeholder engagement. The most promising MU combinations in each sea basin were then summarised, along with the key DABI

Figure 4: Main Opportunities and Challenges of Multi-Use by Joanna Przedzmirska & Emiliano Ramieri

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identified throughout the course of research. The session was concluded with a note of the knowledge gaps preventing MU implementation.

2.3.2 Round Table Discussion and Q&A Session

Participants were grouped according to sea basin to discuss reflections on the MUSES results from each of the EU sea basins and the main opportunities and issues in regards to multi-use implementation, as introduced in the previous presentations (Figure 5). MUSES Partners acted as Table Moderators to facilitate group discussion and answer questions from participants. At the end of the session, each group noted down the “main message” of their discussions: either a key opportunity or issue from the sea basin in question with regards to multi-use development. Main messages are detailed in figure 6 and key elements of discussion aligned well with the findings of the Action Plan.

Figure 5: Participants discussing MUSES results of Sea Basin & Case Study Analysis

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Figure 6: Main messages of Round Table Discussions

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2.4 Session 2A: Multi-Use Perspectives – Tourism-related Multi-Use

2.4.1 Flash Presentations

What does Multi-Use mean for the Tourism sector?

Mara Manente from the International Centre of Studies on the Tourism Economy (CISET) gave a presentation on the competitive conditions of the tourism market in coastal destinations within the Mediterranean and Eastern Atlantic sea basins, and the transnational BLUEMED Initiative for “a new integrated tourism chain”. Shared strategies play a key role in increasing the competitiveness of these

Figure 7: Tourism presentation from Mara Manente

coastal destinations – expanding the tourist products on offer through networks between tourism and other economic sectors (e.g. agriculture, crafts, culture, and fishing) and between destinations. Improving competencies, entrepreneurship and global quality standards within these diverse sectors is also key for the European tourism industry to face the challenges of aggressive competition.

The BLUEMED initiative is a shared strategic framework for working towards a healthy, productive and resilient Mediterranean Sea, involving transnational cooperation to create new ‘blue’ jobs and to promote and improve social wellbeing, sustainable prosperity and the environmental status of the region and its surroundings. The initiative is the result of joint efforts by Cyprus, Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain, with the support of the European Commission, and involves the implementation of four platforms: “Knowledge”, “Technology”, “Economy” and “Policy” required for a new integrated tourism chain in Europe.

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Multi-Use and Underwater Cultural Heritage: Perspectives from the Baltic Sea

Sallamaria Tikkanen of the Finnish Heritage Agency presented on multi-use in relation to Underwater Cultural Heritage (UCH) in the Baltic Sea. The Baltic hosts several exceptionally well preserved UCH, more than half of which are designated monuments and protected. There have been several projects and working groups on UCH in the Baltic, including BalticRIM which integrates cultural heritage into MSP and Baltic Sea Region Working Group on Underwater Cultural Heritage, bringing together a wide range of actors and creating a Code of Good

Practice. Three different examples of UCH and sustainable tourism were then explored, and different elements of each highlighted. The presentation was concluded with a summary of UCH and multi-use, including the best combinations, main challenges and advice, next steps and the roles and partners who should be involved.

Figure 8: UCH Presentation by Sallamaria Tikkanen

Addressing the MU concept with Marine Spatial Planning in the Black Sea

Dr Margarita Stancheva of the Center for Coastal and Marine Studies (CCMS) described how environmental protection and tourism are the key drivers of MU development in the Black Sea, including activities such as ecotourism, underwater adventure tourism, cliff rock climbing, and historical and cultural tourism. The need for regulation of visitors is evident and development is hampered by various factors. Challenges to the concept were explored including lack of approved and operational management plans for protected areas; overbuilding of protected dune and beach areas; unregulated camping and destruction/loss of valuable dune habitats; and lack of sewage systems and degradation of water quality in peak seasons. The SymNet Project was introduced as a good example of much-needed coordinated research into the sustainable development of manufacturing, logistics, and tourism and energy sectors in the Black Sea. MSP in

Figure 9: MSP Presentation by Dr Margarita Stancheva

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the Black Sea is still in its early stages and in process of creating procedures for national MSP development, stakeholder consultation and designating national competent authorities. Kaliakra Nature and Archaeological Reserve serves as an example of MSP being used as a tool for protection and management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and UCH sites through the creation of designated protection zones, special management measures and increased data availability and knowledge. Therefore, MSP has great potential to support MU implementation into the future.

2.4.2 Panel and Q&A

Figure 10: Tourism-related Multi-Use Panel

Panellists included Irina Makarenko (Black Sea Commission), Alda Nikodemusa (Vision and Strategies Around the Baltic sea – VASAB), Dr Vicky Katsoni (University of West Attica), Sallamaria Tikkanen (Finnish Heritage Agency) and Mara Manente (International Centre of Studies on the Tourism Economy – Ciset).

Tourism Session moderator **Helena Calado** (Gaspar Frutuoso Foundation) introduced the panellists and opened the session by asking each of the panellists to give a brief introduction to their views on tourism driven multi-uses. Subsequent questions were also asked on the topics of “overtourism”, “bottom up” approaches to stakeholder engagement and the role of MSP.

In the Mediterranean, **Dr Vicky Katsoni** noted that any future development should consider the carrying capacity of the region. Some places, currently experiencing overtourism, have no further need for development of any kind. Therefore, tourism

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strategies should be considered at national and European level to ensure that development occurs sustainably. Dr Katsoni also noted the importance of a “bottom-up” approach involving local communities in order to resolve conflicts of interest, otherwise the multi-use concept and findings may remain at expert level and inapplicable to society.

Alda Nikodemusa noted that the Action Plan is useful for countries developing and updating their MSPs. The MU concept helps to explain to stakeholders that it's possible to create synergies and this should be capitalised throughout Europe in order to bring sectors and stakeholders together. In the Baltic Sea, there have been a number of multi-use pilots and tourism is becoming increasingly relevant as a sector that planners have to take into consideration.

Mara Manente noted that multi-use is a useful concept but with some conditions, suggesting that less but more profitable tourists are needed. This would involve moving from selling a tourism destination as a commodity to having experiential value – targeting responsible tourists who appreciate the local area. For this, assistance is required from stakeholders at many different levels. Therefore, multi-use is a valid strategy if the overall social and economic improvement of area is considered, not just numbers of tourists.

Irina Makarenko noted that the Action Plan was of great value to the Black Sea where MSP is currently being introduced and that a bottom up approach would be insufficient to involve all stakeholders needed for multi-use to occur successfully. Instead it was noted that the MUSES Action Plan was an excellent approach which found links between sectors and specific stakeholders. This, therefore, would pave the way for discussions about future multi-use.

Sallamaria Tikkanen noted that workshops would be important in involving local stakeholders in multi-use developments. MSP should attempt to involve all multi-use relevant sectors. At present, in Finland, tourism representatives are absent from MSP seminars and other related events. More should therefore be done to ensure that this sector and individual stakeholders are represented.

2.5 Session 2B: Multi-Use Perspectives – Offshore Energy-related Multi-Use

2.5.1 Flash Presentations

Offshore Wind Farms and Seaweed Aquaculture in the Netherlands

Vincent Doumeizel (Lloyd's Register Foundation) & Dr Luc van Hoof (Wageningen University & Research) of the Safe Production Of Marine plants and use of Ocean Space (SOMOS) Project, a partnership between Lloyd's Register Foundation, Wageningen University & Research and TNO, presented on offshore renewable energy production in combination with seaweed. Issues in the current food supply chain were discussed before demonstrating how “seagriculture” could be used as a sustainable food source, with a variety of economic benefits.

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Figure 11: SOMOS Presentation, Vincent Doumeizel

When combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture, safety concerns of both developers must be addressed. The SOMOS Project has therefore developed a safety framework for addressing conditions at sea, related to this multi-use. The presentation concluded with a reminder to participants about the SOMOS Project sponsored presentation and reception following the MUSES final conference.

Multi-Use Potential in the North Sea

Nathalie Scheidegger of the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality and **Nico Buytendijk** of the Netherlands Enterprise Agency presented on the Dutch North Sea Strategy 2030 and Community of Practice (CoP). For the strategy to be a success, it is important for collaboration between such policy makers and implementation agencies of policy. An overview was given on the Dutch North Sea Strategy 2030: the ministries involved, the three transitions and the strong involvement of stakeholders. The aim of the CoP is to facilitate the further development of offshore energy in the busy North Sea, including those involving multi-use, bringing together the knowledge and connections of a variety of different North Sea actors (including policy makers, research organisations, entrepreneurs and NGOs) to discuss a variety of important topics. The CoP therefore helps make the step from theory to practice for a variety of different ocean uses – including seaweed farms, mussel aquaculture and solar energy at sea.

Figure 12: Multi-Use in the North Sea Presentation by Nathalie Scheidegger and Nico Buytendijk

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Oil & Gas Decommissioning – opportunities for reuse and repurposing

Prof. Catrinus Jepma of the Energy Delta Institute presented on the potential for repurposing decommissioned Oil and Gas (O&G) fields in the North Sea to make the production of offshore renewable energy and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) more economically feasible. For offshore renewable energy, instead of transporting electricity produced directly to shore (which necessitates expensive new electricity cables), it could be converted into hydrogen gas on an offshore platform and subsequently transported using the current O&G infrastructure. The production of this “green” hydrogen is almost as economically competitive as traditional “blue” and “grey” hydrogen and less environmentally unfriendly. In terms of CCS, the North Sea and its existing O&G infrastructure is in close proximity to where the majority of European CO₂ is produced. It is therefore well positioned to channel and store CO₂ under the sea using the existing gas pipeline network. O&G decommissioning therefore provides an affordable means of developing these two uses.

Figure 13: O&G Decommissioning Presentation by Prof. Catrinus Jepma

Offshore Wind/Wave farms and mussel aquaculture in the UK

Figure 14: Offshore wind/wave & Mussel Aquaculture Presentation by James Wilson

James Wilson of Deepdock Ltd, a mussel aquaculture developer, presented on their experience of initiating multi-use with offshore wind developers. The theory of combining offshore wind farms with aquaculture is a positive one – the aquaculture developers benefit from big shipping being kept away from the site and also mitigate biofoul from the wind farms. However, in practice, there is too much uncertainty and not enough incentives for offshore wind developers to express a real interest in multi-use. Risks of uncertainty work both ways – issues of access and safety of vessels are of particular concern to the offshore wind developer whereas economic uncertainty of how to get aquaculture products to market from exposed offshore areas is of paramount importance to the aquaculture company. In order to make progress, the issue of mutual benefit must be resolved; research is needed to address uncertainties; relationships must be built and maintained between

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the two developers; and policy guidance and better understanding of the regulatory framework with regards to the multi-use is needed.

Role of Ocean Clusters

Figure 15: Ocean Clusters Presentation by Julie Person

Julie Person of Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM) presented on the role of ocean clusters in supporting multi-use development of the ocean. PMM is a sea innovation and business cluster which supports innovative collaborative projects, including offshore renewable energies and sustainable fishing and aquaculture. For example, for the development of a floating offshore wind farm in Occitanie, PMM provided a platform for different stakeholders to meet, mapped the

actors and skills to identify the supply chain and co-organised a conference on floating offshore wind turbines, attended by over 1000 stakeholders. PMM was also a partner in the PELAGOS Project to promote networks and clusters of marine renewables in several Mediterranean countries and involved in an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) and offshore wind collaboration to cultivate mussels alongside wind farms. Several barriers were faced to the IMTA project including regulatory procedures and insurance issues for combined uses and hostility of fishers to losing their traditional fishing zones.

2.5.2 Panel and Q&A

Panellists included Maarten Flikkema (MARIN), Leo de Vrees (Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management), Dr Silvia Grandi (Italian Ministry of Economic Development), Dale Rodmell (National Federation of Fishermen's Organisations – NFFO), David Campbell (Albatern Ltd) and James Wilson (Deepdock Ltd).

Offshore Energy Session moderator **Andronikos Kafas** (Marine Scotland) introduced the panellists and opened the session by asking each of the panellists to give a brief introduction to their views and experiences on offshore energy driven multi-uses. Subsequent questions were also asked on the topics of responsibility for risks moving further offshore and how to attract large companies to invest in multi-use ventures.

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Figure 16: Offshore Energy-related Multi-Use Panel

Dr Silvia Grandi pointed out that while there are many examples of multi-use, reapplying them in different context proves an issue. What is needed is for every country to develop their own plans and encourage entrepreneurship, while developing and sharing scientific and other multi-use relevant knowledge. As most of these uses occur in often harsh offshore locations the issue of safety is paramount – both of people and the environment.

David Campbell of Albatern Ltd (a wave energy company, combining with aquaculture) revealed that their main concern was how to get as quickly and as safely as possible from concept to practice. Regulation is an issue as not much is known about the risks and different licensing procedures for aquaculture and wave energy developments further complicate matters. The venture is costly and therefore not commercially viable for small projects and commercial and real risk means that insurers suffer losses as aquaculture moves further offshore.

James Wilson noted that the theory of MSP is useful and related to multi-use in terms of efficient use of marine space; however, much more work is required to “catch up” to multi-use in terrestrial planning where it is more predominant, despite relatively rigid planning controls.

Maarten Flikkema, who works on the Space@Sea Project, talked about their development of modular multi-application platforms whereby small modular components (floating islands) connect to make one big island. Such a platform can potentially host multiple applications – combining uses such as fish farming, service

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of offshore wind farms and generation of offshore wind energy – thereby contributing to multi-use of ocean space.

Leo de Vrees stated the importance of promoting multi-use business cases – many multi-use projects are still in the pilot phase and more commercial interest and investment is needed to make real progress. Regional differences should be taken into account and areas suitable for certain types of multi-use identified. There are still many risks to tackle and it must be considered how to divide these – something that needs to be facilitated by governments.

Dale Rodmell stated that, for the fishing industry, safety issues are the number one priority – with cables from offshore wind farms as one of the biggest concerns. As fishing is a very distributed sector, they are more likely to come into contact with other uses. The development of productive working relationships which recognise each other's interests, from industry to industry, is important. This has developed over time with the Oil and Gas sector since discovery in the North Sea. Thus far, the narrative of multi-use has focused on impact mitigation for fishers (i.e. dealing with negative consequences). What is needed for the future is promotion of coexistence and a more positive policy and legislative framework to support this.

2.6 Session 3: The MUSES Multi-Use Action Plan

2.6.1 Overview of the MUSES Multi-Use Action Plan

Angela Schultz-Zehden (SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth) introduced the MUSES Multi-Use Action Plan which provides actions and recommendations on what should be done, and by whom, in order to further develop the Multi-Use concept. The Action Plan is highly pertinent in the wider context of the Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) Directive, blue investment and Sustainable Development Goals and addresses barriers relating not only to technology, but also regulatory, financing, liability issues, environmental concerns, stakeholder perceptions and capacity building.

Multi-Use implies a radical change from traditional single sector approaches and to occur requires interest from (a) at least both uses involved or (b) one use and the regulatory body. Based on systematic research and stakeholder input, the Action Plan covers nine Multi-Use combinations – a selection of the wide ranging multi-use opportunities available. For each Multi-Use, the Action Plan details (i) the definition/ scope of the multi-use, (ii) its state of development and future potential, (iii) Drivers, Added values, Barriers and negative Impacts (DABI), (iv) logical framework and objectives and (v) the action and recommendations required to further develop the multi-use.

Figure 17: Action Plan Presentation by Angela Schultz-Zehden

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From across all nine multi-uses, six key cross-cutting issues and actions were identified:

- Integration and coordination
- Policy, regulation & MSP
- Capacity building
- Marketing & dissemination
- Funding
- Research

A number of relevant actors and institutions targeted by the Action Plan were highlighted, including international and EU wide institutions, blue growth forums, planning and regulatory authorities, research institutions, funding and finance, industry, stakeholder networks, insurance companies, civil society and local enterprises and actors. Lastly, participants were reminded that the full Action Plan and Executive Summary would be available on the MUSES website: <https://musesproject.eu/downloads/> .

2.6.2 Round Table Discussions

Participants were split into groups for discussion on the Action Plan, and associated actions. Discussion leads (both external stakeholders and MUSES partners) supported discussion through the following questions:

- Which actions do/don't you support; which actions would be particularly difficult?
- What are the main enablers for undertaking these actions?
- What type of commitments could your individual organisations make with regards to multi use?
- Have you identified some commitments of joint interest at your table?
- Would you promote the action plan – how? How should we promote it?

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- Have you perhaps identified some opportunities for future collaboration with regards to multi-use at your table?

Figure 18: Participants discuss the MUSES Multi-Use Action Plan

Following on from this structured discussion, participants were asked to rate actions according to level of impact relative to the level of effort required to achieve them, and the order in which these should be achieved. Each discussion lead recorded the multi-use combinations discussed at their table and well as their key discussion points and observations. Ordering the timeline of actions proved to be quite challenging; however, participants engaged in deep discussions on action impact vs effort. The main statements were collated from the tables and are summarised below.

High Impact/ Low Effort

- Develop a community of practice on multi-use and marketing of this to relevant actors
- Facilitate capacity building, especially related to tourism-related multi-uses
- Use of social media to disseminate information about multi-use to relevant actors
- Early communication and involvement of different stakeholders in MSP
- Capacity building of MSP authorities in terms of promoting multi-use
- Demonstrating the added value of multi-use

Low Impact/ Low Effort

- Learning from MSP plans from other countries and how they developed their multi-use policies
- More academic literature on multi-use

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- Small incentives for fishers etc to branch into tourism-related multi-uses
- Improving regulation of multi-use at national level
- Strategic environmental assessments for multi-use
- Individual organisations promoting multi-use

High Impact/ High Effort

- Financing a pilot to demonstrate that multi-use can be done in a safe and sustainable manner
- Commissioning designs for synergies
- Streamlining legislation and regulation – administrative integration
- Making multi-use compulsory
- Making multi-use meta-data available on one platform
- Embed multi-use recommendations in a legislative framework for multi-use of space
- Developing scientific knowledge required for technological development of multi-uses
- Funding for projects
- Bottom-up approaches
- Getting governments to take responsibility for promoting multi-use and taking action
- Development of multi-use specific EU regulations
- Innovation clusters

Low Impact/ High Effort

participants felt that this was largely superfluous to discuss, as actions having low impact are not worth of high efforts to be implemented

2.7 Session 4: Closing Panel on promoting Multi-Use and next steps

Panellists included Dr Felix Leinemann (Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries – DG MARE), Dr Nikos Zampoukas (Directorate General for Research and Innovation – DG Research), Dr Steven Degraer (Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences – RBINS), Dr Wei He (Equinor) and Marina Markovic (Priority Actions Programme Regional Activity Centre – PAP/RAC).

Action Plan Session moderator **Angela Schultz-Zehden** (SUBMARINER) introduced the panellists and opened the session by asking each of the panellists to give their take home message from the Multi-Use Action Plan. Subsequent questions were also asked on the role of nature conservation and involving industry in multi-use conversations.

Marina Markovic noted that integration and coordination are highly promoted in the Action Plan and recognises this is the first precondition for enabling multi-use. In the Mediterranean, there are high levels of development over the entire coastal area which serves as a driver for multi-use.

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Dr Wei He contested earlier discussions in the conference that there is a lack of industry involvement in the MUSES final conference and multi-use in general – rather experiencing active participation of industry in MUSES and previous projects. Also noted was the utility of applying Oil and Gas knowledge in offshore wind development.

Figure 19: Closing Panel on Promoting Multi-Use

Dr Steven Degraer noted the difficulty of prioritising actions within the Action Plan and suggested we do everything in our power to achieve as much as possible, starting now. Further involvement of industrial partners would be beneficial for this, given their greater resources. Also noted was that we should be more ambitious and active promote nature conservation as part of multi-use, rather than merely focusing on avoiding and mitigating impacts. For the future there are possibilities to create win-win situations where nature conservation acts as facilitator for new uses and, for example, integrating wind farms into nature conservation areas.

Dr Nikos Zampoukas observed that while the market is not fully ready to integrate multi-use, the Action Plan goes a long way – highlighting, for example, barriers to technological innovation. There is potential for wind farms to be developed in the Mediterranean and Black seas and investment plans are needed for this to become a reality. One of the most difficult factors for multi-use may be to get people from different sectors side-by-side (most challenging for aquaculture and tourism agencies). For the next funding call – Horizon Europe – aquaculture, offshore energy and maritime tourism are high on the agenda, and plans for common clusters for aquaculture and fisheries are being considered. The work of MUSES and the Action Plan will be taken into consideration for this.

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Dr Felix Leinemann noted that MSP is the one piece of legislation that could help to achieve the majority of the actions in the Action Plan by “facilitating the coexistence of uses” at national level. In the future, the blue economy and offshore energy will develop extensively. He also stated that “only by combining uses can we positively benefit from this”. Also noted were the economic benefits of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), especially to tourism, on which the European Commission recently published a study. Of note in the future are the Bioeconomy and Atlantic Strategies, currently in revision which are taking into consideration maritime activities and the role of MSP respectively. The European Maritime and Fisheries Fund are to continue to fund FLAGs to help remote communities with revenue.

Final comments to round up the session included:

- the need for clear rules on licensing, funding, monitoring activities – what is working/ not working and how we can improve
- taking actions to integrate multi-use into significant future uses including offshore wind development and reuse of decommissioned platforms
- the need for extensive promotion and dissemination of the multi-use concept, including pilot projects, to show that multi-use works and that there are clear financial benefits
- the FLAGs concept should go further than just fisheries and aquaculture to encompass the entire blue economy and be used to show examples of multi-use and associated benefits to local communities and economies.

Angela Schultz-Zehden then concluded the session by emphasising the ongoing commitments of MUSES partners, conference participants and other relevant stakeholders to keep building discussions and actions on multi-use.

2.8 Closing Remarks

Phil Gilmour closed the conference thanking all those involved over the course of the MUSES project for their role in shifting the culture of marine development from single use to multi-use implementation, including the European Commission and Project Officer, the MUSES consortium and participants at the final conference and other stakeholder workshops. The resultant Action Plan is important in the process of further disseminating and promoting multi-use. For future development, an opportunistic approach is required which targets developers and promotes pilot research.

2.9 SOMOS Reception

After the closing of the MUSES Project Final Conference, the SOMOS (Safe production Of Marine plants and use of Ocean Space) Project hosted a celebratory closing reception aimed at disseminating their project results and informal discussions on multi-use. The SOMOS Project is co-funded by Lloyds Register Foundation, Wageningen Research and TNO, not by Horizon 2020, and this was made clear to participants in the agenda.

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3. Conference Outcomes and Follow-up

The conference proceedings and discussions have been detailed in this report. While these results cannot be included within the scope of the MUSES Project Action Plan, which has already been published, it is our expectation that the discussions initiated within the final conference will now be continued and information disseminated with those from outside the conference community in order to facilitate the actions required to promote future multi-use.

Following the conference all participants were sent electronic copies of the full Multi-Use Action Plan and Executive Summary, all presentations and all posters on display. All of these documents have been made available in the downloads section of the MUSES website: <https://muses-project.eu/downloads/>

All presentations referred to in this report can be found at:
<https://muses-project.eu/downloads/>

MUSES partners would like to thank all those attending and contributing to the conference. We hope this event will be rich in fruitful discussions, offer great networking opportunities and provide a platform for future collaborations and ideas.

